
COPYRIGHT LAW: ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY OF LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract:

In our digital age, information transmission and information protection are equally important. For instance, information and communication technologies enable online information access, but they also make it difficult for authors and other producers to safeguard their ideas and works. Professionals in libraries are essential in ensuring that information is protected and shared without violating copyright. The current study covers the difficulties with copyright in the digital age, copyright problems with library services, and the duties of librarians in upholding copyright law. There is just one law protecting the works of authors or other creators, despite the fact that digitization, preservation, archives, the internet, and open access are all in copyright violation frenzy. Consequently, librarians should play a part in upholding copyright laws in this digital age.

Keywords: *Copyright; Fair Use; ICT; Library and Information Center; Library Professionals.*

Introduction:

The advancement of information and communication technology and internet information can easily accessible for users, though author or creator also has to take strong steps to secure their work in this digital age. Copyright law protects their work with legal provisions but somehow the advancement of technology make exception to access copyrighted information. Therefore library and information professional's role has been changed in this era they have to keep them aware about

copyright law, illegal issues, reproduction and communication of information.

The digitization techniques and popularity of social media raised many difficulties for authors and creators. The innovation of technology gives exceptional opportunities to the users to access copyrighted information therefore copyright related issues has been increased. Now a days sharing, dissemination and reproduction of information through legal channel is a big challenge for library and information science professionals. As a LIS professionals should have copyright literacy

with them for fair use and sharing of information.

Copyright highlighted by Irish King Diarmid in 6th century A.D with his slogan “To every cow her calf; therefore to every author his copy.”(<http://www.ifla.org>) Copyright gives legal rights to the author or creator to publish their own work. The primary objectives of copyright to promote the progress of science and useful arts, by securing for limited times to author and inventors one exclusive right to their respective writing and discoveries(Ramana, 2004).copyright law protect owner from an illegal exploitation and reproduction of his work.

Copyright is a highlighted component in every institution. Copyright literacy is become essential thing for library and information science professionals to handle copyright related issues in the library and also make themselves aware about copyright polices and provisions. Copyright literacy includes acquisition and presentation of skills and knowledge to encourage ethical creation and use of copyright documents. Present study will focus on the assessment of awareness among the LIS professionals in University libraries in Maharashtra and also discuss the reason of violation copyright, copyright literacy programs, copyright policies and practices.

Copyright:

According to World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) “copyright is a legal term describing rights given to creators for their literary and artistic works. Copyright is a form of protection provided by the laws of any country to the authors of “original works of authorship,” including

literary, dramatic, musical, artistic, and certain other intellectual work. (www.lib.neu.edu/tutorials/glossary.html).

According to Library Gateway of University of Illinois copyright is,” the legal right to control the production, use, and sale of copies of a literary, musical, or artistic Work.(www.lib.neu.edu/tutorials/glossary.html)Copyright protects authors or creator ideas and allows them to sell, print and publish their own work.(Burchfiel, 1989)

The following works covered under copyright law

1. Original literary works;
2. Dramatic works, including any accompanying music
1. Musical works, including any accompanying works;
3. Pantomimes and choreographic works;
4. Pictorial, graphic, and sculptural works;
5. Motion pictures and other audiovisual works;
6. Sound recordings;
7. Architectural works.

Need of Awareness among the LIS Professionals:

The application of copyright laws and provisions to grant access, replication, and reprinting of documents in libraries is the requirement of this era. Library and information science professionals learn about copyright law and fair use of documents through their curriculum. Every day, new technological advancements make it simpler to access, copy, and duplicate an author's work. Since these are the primary channels for copying and transforming resources, the development of digitization

techniques and social media applications raises a number of challenges for writers and editors. Information brokers, or LIS professionals, are key players in the communication of information. Therefore, it's important to keep students informed about copyright rules and appropriate usage of library resources.

Copyright Policy and Use of Library Services:

Initially, copyright law only applied to the copying of books, but with the development of technology and digitization techniques, new issues arose, such as translation, derivative works, copying, and reproduction of documents. As a result, copyright protection for fair use of documents has been strengthened. Librarians serve as custodians of knowledge and resources, and they frequently deal with intellectual property rights and copyright issues in the course of providing library services. Librarians and information professionals must strike a balance between the author's or creator's and the user's interests. Furthermore, the institute's research outcomes are dependent on improved information services from the library and information centres. Before beginning any library services for their users, library professionals must consider copyright violations and fair use of documents. Every library and information centre should have a fair use policy in place for library patrons. It will improve ethical access to library resources. The library and information centre are divided into several sections to provide better services to users, but such sections, such as "periodical/journal section," "thesis and

dissertation section," "Old and Rare Book Section," and "Repositories and e-resources," are more likely to violate copy rights. As a result, all such sections require copyright protection for better document preservation and dissemination. For fair use of library resources, libraries and information centres should have their own copyright policy.

Challenges In Digital Era:

Technology innovation has enhanced the reproduction, copying, and transformation of copyrighted content. Because digital content can be duplicated essentially for free and with no quality loss, the author and distributors were unable to stop the practice. Technology has two uses: it may be used to readily make information available to the public and to limit it from illegal access. The main issue is that current regulation has not succeeded in keeping information out of the hands of computer programmes and networked systems. Obtaining copyright authorization is one of the mentioned difficulties in developing a digital library. Inferences between laws and digital creation raised the following issues:

- Also, the reformatting of data or materials to make them available shouldn't be viewed as a violation of copyright laws but rather as reasonable access.
- A single copyright law should handle digital and printed content equally, and national legislation should take into account all factors at the national and international levels.
- In contrast to the restrictions set forth by copyright laws, there should be a straightforward payment system.

- Users get free access to publicly available copyrighted content as well as works in digital format.
- Read, hear, or watch publicly marketed copyright content in private, locally or online.
- For personal, academic, or research use, the library and information staff copied an acceptable amount of copyrighted content. (Dominic, 2003).

Role and Responsibilities of Library Professionals in Prevention of Copyright Law:

In this digital age libraries are engaged in providing instant access of information but in same way they need to aware about copyright law while sharing and using of documents. The role of library and information science professionals has been changed with invention of digital technology, electronic publication of documents, social media and smart phone. Library users are unaware about copyright law hence they feel that every is accessible but as a library professionals they should orient them to fair use of document, copyright policies, terms and condition for access e resources through web. Library professionals should gain knowledge about dissemination; reproduction and communication of resources without violation of copyright law and also LIS professional make them strengthen to draw a copy right policy for fair use of resources and protection of copyright law. The following points describe role of library professionals in this electronic environment:

- Create a copyright policy for fair use of library resources.

- Make awareness among the user about copy right, legal use of document, e resources access policies, copying of print document and sharing of information.
- The subscribed e-journals should use only academic and research purpose.
- Orient users about access policy of library for e journals, e books and online data bases.
- Keep update about new amendment of copy right and follow the publisher and distributors policies
- Allow user to take one print out of electronic publication for academic and research purpose
- Restrict user to download entire issues of journals or to copy entire print journal issues
- Restrict user download, share and copy of entire e-book.
- Arrange awareness program for library user of copyright literacy and fair use of library resources
- Display the copyright instruction for user to prevent copyright and illegal access of information. (<https://www.gateway.library.uiuc.edu/learn/orientation/glossary.html>)

Conclusion:

New ways to use copyrighted works online and off have emerged as a result of the development of information and communication technology. Authors, inventors, and artists may be fair about their work and protect their ideas since it enables users to reproduce, manipulate, and distribute their work with the least amount of effort and expense. Strict copyright laws

are needed in this digital age to safeguard authors and other creative. Because librarians play a crucial role in the transmission of information, it is our fundamental responsibility as library professionals to preserve copyrighted material.

The repositories of knowledge and information are the library and information centres. Copyright violations are more likely to occur here than everywhere else. The professions of libraries must therefore continue to promote the preservation and fair use of library resources.. (Saikia & Eqbal, 2012)

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